

Article

“Promoting participation and success for children with Cerebral Palsy in Arts Education Programmes of Music”

Appendix 1

Table 1 - Objectives and questions to ask Parents of children with CP

Objectives	Questions
Objective1: To introduce, ‘break the ice’ and get to know the image that Parents have of their child, their development, daily life at home and their characteristics	p1. I'd like you to start by telling us a bit about your child. What are his/her defining characteristics?
Objective2: Identify what interests the child and what they like to do, to better characterise the child taking part in the study	p2. What activities does he/she like to do? What are your child's interests? What are your child's strengths? Could you tell me?
Objective3: To check whether Parents are aware of how their child assimilates knowledge, whether they think they learn and how they learn, as well as to record Parents' representations of their children's learning and contribute to characterising the children	p3. How does your child access knowledge? How do they most like to learn, study texts, videos, images, etc?
Objective4: Identify what Parents perceive as necessary for their child to learn better (what Parents miss to enhance their child's learning)	p4. What could facilitate your child's learning at school/home and access to school or other content?
Objective5: Check whether Parents are aware of Technologies: Digital Technologies (DT) and Assistive Technology (AT) (even those that are digitally based), and how and how regularly they use them (frequency of use, alone, with Parents, with siblings, only at school, etc.)	p5. Does your child use DT/AT daily? If so, which ones? How? In what contexts?
Objective6: Identify what kind of artistic activities children with CP attend, in what contexts, where, how and with whom	p6. Does your child have access to artistic and musical activities? Which ones? Where? How? With whom?
Objective7: To check whether Parents are aware of the type of adaptations that are possible so that their child can have access to artistic/musical activities	p7. In your opinion, what kind of adaptations can facilitate the process of including your child in artistic/musical activities?
Objective8: Open questions for any issues that Parents feel are relevant to raise	p8. Are there any other aspects that you think are important to mention?

Appendix 2

Table 2 - Objectives and questions for MP working with children with EN

Objectives	Questions
Objective 1: To introduce, 'break the ice' and get to know the respondents' professional activity	p1. Tell us a little about your professional experience in teaching music or music therapy.
Objective 2: To find out what level of knowledge the MP interviewed consider they have about the use of Technology. Digital Technology (DT) or Assistive Technology (AT) in their professional practices	p2. What do you consider to be your level of knowledge about Technology? DT and AT that can be used to promote the Learning of children with EN?
Objective 3: To ascertain the level of knowledge and experience that the MP interviewed have regarding the use of AT in their professional practices. To identify the degree of familiarity they have with the concepts of DT, AT, software, etc.	p3. In line with the previous question: a) Do you know of any DT to support music teaching for students with EN? Can you specify? c) What AT do you know? Can you specify? However, d) Which DT or AT have you used or felt the need to use in the development of your classes or therapies? Why? Which ones? How? Can you specify?
Objective4: To ascertain the interviewees' awareness of the accessibility of their practices. To gather information on how teachers deal with the issue of inclusion and accessibility and to what extent they feel prepared to include children with EN	p4. How do you ensure that the artistic, musical or therapy activities you carry out professionally are accessible to students with EN? Can you specify?
Objective5: Identify the experience that MP has in their practice with children with motor and communication limitations due to CP	p5. Have you ever worked with pupils with motor and communication difficulties due to CP? In what contexts?
Objective6: To find out what adaptations MP have had to make to achieve results in the learning or therapy of their pupils/patients	p6. What adaptations have you had to make to your teaching or therapy methods?
Objective7: Identify the results they achieved with the adaptations they implemented in their practice, and, above all, what needs they felt	p7. What difficulties or added value have resulted from the adaptations you have made to your practice?
Objective8: Open questions for any issues that the MP consider relevant and not covered by the questions posed	p8. Are there any other aspects that you think are important to mention?